

Is there a Bioinformatic Entropy in Cosmoconsciousness?-Proposal for Experimental Trials

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ABSTRACT

With the premise of biochemical stimuli universally acting upon biochemistry, the research hypothesizes a bioinformatic entropy in the cosmological sciences that influences the consciousness structure with psychological time through the neuron network. Experiment trials in developmental psychology are proposed to further determine the epistemological correlations between cognition in cosmoconsciousness and the independent variables in spatial adjacency in time series. The experiment proposed purposes to supplement the knowledge gap between the matter-dependent definition of time, and time as a reception consciousness from the cosmological influences. The bioinformatic entropy is thus defined as psychological time in conscious phenomena, with cosmic stimuli differing in intensities determining neuritogenesis in DNA dimorphism in developmental psychology. The transdisciplinary experiment aims to draw an initial correlation, quantitatively, between cosmological developments and biochemistry in determining the gaps between informatics technologies and human psycho-physiology in a common cosmic environment. The experiment proposed explores the active consciousness and is a paradigm shift to the passive consciousness in Darwinian biogenesis.

Keywords: Psychological time; Cosmoconsciousness; Bioinformatic entropy; Developmental psychology; Neuritogenesis, Cosmic stimuli

INTRODUCTION

Research scope

The primary question the experiment seeks to answer is “how much, if any, do the scientists’ biochemical influence in scientific activities contribute to cosmological predictions?” The question will be answered with the cosmological data and predictions of scientific theories to the scientists’ data’s correlations to the adjacent residents’ biochemical developments, by the corrective factors with the scientists’ consciousness differences in biochemistry. With the answers in the primary question, a secondary question on the sociology of knowledge can be drawn “do the common beliefs with collective consciousness driving collective actions have an influence to epistemological biases?” The question has universalizable values, even though may vary by organizational types and methods, on collective unconsciousness in developmental psychology with the objective evidences’ parameterization, and may apply to the global systems of values. The tertiary question is “to what directions can we improve our current cosmological theories?” The question will be answered

with further statistical data in DNA as modern humans involved in the experiment on the evolutionary biology’s conformability with cosmological and gravitational theories, correcting the gaps between technological objectivity and consciousness phenomena involved in scientific activities. I believe that a cosmological theory should be able to explain, at least quantitatively, biology; and by Karl Popper’s falsification principle, replacing inter-rater reliability with the positivism in subjective epistemology, the study seeks to reduce the subjective biases in the ranges of cosmological theories with myself included. The direction to the current study may have been influenced by the author’s previous report on the thermonuclear contamination of outer space with local black holes and white holes [1], unconsciously or subconsciously for a salvageable path.

Purpose and objective

The research aims to uncover the unconscious elements in modern science, and questions into “what time is”. With the current technological construct, cosmological science mainly relies on the optical stimuli on the scientists for observational feedback

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and knowledge production, with the latter heavily relying on the sociology of knowledge and correspondence theory of truth for validation [2], which are normally in linguistic-informatics contexts. The research theorizes the objective epistemology that, in cosmological sciences, the subjective developmental psychology in the biochemistry of scientists and sociology of knowledge can be a bias factor for the advancement of the cosmological science, or the natural and social sciences in general. The purpose of the experiment is to gather objective evidence for the theorization, so that further meta-epistemological feedback can be established between cosmology and biochemistry for the evaluation [3].

The objective of the research is the earth-centric equalities of the independent and dependent variables' biochemical starting points with environmental factors, with the independent variables' active participations in the cosmological and nuclear science activities. With environmental correlations, the factors in developmental psychology can be extracted; and with non-human correlations, the cosmological theories' retrogressive statistical conformity to human development can be further corroborated and corrective to the cosmological sciences' developments. The implications of the objective are: a) Science management with relation to existing and emerging technologies; b) The cosmological sciences' indicative and predicative feedback to the environmental and biochemical sciences for human welfare; c) An objective approach to epistemology in collective activities that may be universalizable to organizational methods across disciplines; d) Development in astrobiology.

Properties of quantum systems

From the measurements of time in the historic and modern derivatives, constituents of matter and physical laws have been the standards of units on the concept of time. This inevitably introduced entropy into the measurements of time and the conscious experiences of time implied. While epistemology has been a philosophical topic on science for centuries, an objective epistemic approach to consciousness has only been a recent phenomenon with the developments in clinical biochemistry. The quantitative approach adopted by Vazza, et al. [4], between the cosmic web and neuronal network with cerebellar cortex stimuli applied to brain chemistry plotted against the distribution of dark matter implies a natural correlation between unconscious brain developments to the density power spectrum from dark matter components with baryon genesis. Inspired by their work in the optic band with a question in physical entropy on the concept of time, the research changed the question on the concept of time to the question in developmental psychology, with the optical stimuli considered as receptive consciousness from cosmological influences. Vazza, et al. [4], stated that their studies in brain science focused on the cytoplasmic compartment of the neurons and highest stain density located at the level of neuronal soma, implying the correlation of natural waves to the interference of neuron balance in brain development with carbon dimorphism. From the neutron asymmetry in proton decay in the universe [5], the hypothesis is raised that there could have been a biochemical correlation between carbon dimorphism in brain development and the cosmological development of the universe. Since the works of Vazza, et al. [4], adapted cosmological data with simulation to brain samples in optical images implying a cosmological influence perspective to the question, I seek to

further determine the causality in brain biochemistry to the epistemology between environmental factors and non-human factors in cosmoconsciousness for a fundamental research on the correspondence theory of truth [2]. Table 1 summarizes the factors to be determined in conscious phenomena to the differences in the cosmological interpretations, and the randomized trials of (Vazza, et al. [4], Vazza, personal communication, "the two datasets were acquired by entirely different people in entirely different ways", October 28, 2022) have preliminarily drawn the level-1 environmental factor to level 1 non-human factors (F. Vazza, personal communication, "no wavelengths whatsoever associated with the latter", October 28, 2022).

The neuron soma results from Vazza, et al. [4], may have implied that the correlation of natural waves to the interference of brainwaves exists, even when it led "to a non-standard definition of nodes". The cosmological hypothesis is set with the proton decay qualitative microscopic nuclear cosmic forces to the perturbations to earth in natural environmental interference of wave-functions [5], causing the phenomenon of time in the current SI Unit definitions [6].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and sampling strategy

The study involves a qualitative design in cosmology and a quantitative design in biochemical psychology. The designs in experiment trials mainly follow a psychological experiment method, qualitatively guided by the cosmological science. The study theorizes a proton decay model in cosmology that governs human physiological development and neuritogenesis from DNA to cell division. The design transcends the ethnographic and hereditary concepts in biological studies, and presumes a quantitative equality in developmental biochemistry with regard to cosmological influences. The experiment trials seek to gather primary data for further correlative analysis between catalysis in human biochemical development and cosmology from neurite-soma brain development. Correlative correctional factors in the experiment trials are designed for the independent variables of the scientists in the fields as the human factor, to the environmental and non-human factors in the dependent variables, such as the differences in interference of brainwaves to natural waves and instrumentation generated waves between the independent and dependent variables in developmental psychology. This involves indicators in brain chemistry with the presumption that the differences in individual DNAs do not influence the developmental psychology much as to the cosmological influences in the environmental factors. Apart from astronomical and cosmological data in time series and their projections to the earth's space that are needed for the experiments, a combination of MRI, EGG, and PET techniques is the primary materials for biochemical data gathering for the experiment trials [7]. A continuous three-year study is planned for the experiment trials, in parallel to the analysis and necessary readjustment. The key focus is the cosmic decay's roles to biochemistry with the nuclear forces.

The sampling strategy is based on the developmental psychological differences from professional activities of the participants in the experiment trials. They are grouped by the criteria of: a) Active differences—neurite development differences by daily/

professional activities; b) Passive indifference—natural exposure to geocentrically fixed influences from the cosmos; c) Variants in passive differences—differences to exposures to other interference to brainwaves in professional activities such as electromagnetism and radioactivity in the nuclear and/or cosmological sciences; d) Variants in active differences—intellectually intensive professions vs. bodily active intensive professions. The criteria, when vertically analysed through the cosmological data, will further dissect the contribution of cosmic influences and conscious activities' influences to biological and biochemical developments in the human bodies, with the passive indifferences as the baseline for analysis. The passive indifferences will be corrected with gender differences, which may contribute to the differences in the indifferent unconsciousness from the cosmological influences.

Data collection

The data collection method was inspired by the mini-review on the environmental physiological impact analysis of electronic warfare on the biochemical integrity of public health [8]. The conceptualization of the thermonuclear processes in biochemistry was correlated to the proton decay cosmic analysis on the cosmic forces. However, due to the gaps between exhaustibility in observation and effects in the phenomenon of time, how to aggregate the qualitative research to a quantitative one became the question for data collection. The data collection adopts mixed methods on focused groups in the experiment trials with elements in self-reports and questionnaires in biochemical exposure history with consciousness on the beliefs in the concept of time, and interviews with the independent variables in the experiment trials are ideally to be correlated with their individual primary data in observations. The latter can have a direct correlative primary source between the independent and dependent variables, and the data collection will be dependent on the participating scientists' research and mission periods either active or archival. Apart from the differences in angular momenta and times series in observations, cosmological and astronomical data collected within the years gaps within half a century will be considered gravitationally stable from the local universes' sources. Depending on the wavelengths of the independent variables' expertise, supplementary data gathering for multispectral analysis will be performed, with consideration to the independent variables' inter-rater complementarities. Since the cosmic sources' gravitational force effects longitudinally asserting on earth are reduced in lengths from the local universes, even if limited to a geographical area, the proton decay model qualitatively analysed with secondary observations from space-based telescopes and primary observations with Harvard-Smithsonian Micro Observatory [5], grey matter cleavages' details will be compared with selectable sources' nuclear force trails with data gathered either from the participating scientists and/or the publicly available data products from institutions under the NASA contracts.

The original data will be collected from the experiment trials designed, with the quantitative cosmological data applied to the experiment trials. The data collection method adopted seeks to dissect brain development from epistemological differences, and consciousness phenomena in the astronomical and

cosmological sciences to the objectivity of scientific knowledge, such as the definition of time in conscious phenomena of the SI unit definitions in NIST [6], "unperturbed ground-state hyperfine transition frequency of the cesium 133 atom", to the causal impact from receptive consciousness of the universe. For the purpose, dependent variables are designed to the non-scientist groups with the specific meaning in the astronomical and cosmological sciences, which constitute the independent variables. The independent variables' brain biochemistry will be compared with their astronomical and cosmological research data, which constitute the secondary independent variable to be tested with controlled trials of the dependent variables. With the considerations of developmental biophysiology, the dependent variables are initially conceptualized into professionals in sports and martial arts, and adjacent residents to the independent variables. The latter determines the environmental factors and the former the non-human factors. This dissects the variables to stimuli in optic nerves with a presumption of universality in brain and neural development from birth, and developmental differences in neural development due to differences in brain biochemical developments. The CO₂ determinant in physiological phase transitions between consciousness and unconsciousness [9], is controlled within the presumption of the earth's atmosphere with global distribution in cosmology, and more detailed quantitative determinants, if needed, can be correlated to Greenhouse Gas Emission data with surveys on residential histories. With the cosmic causalities and sun's rays' distribution on the earth's surface, time is not sequential as it appears to the bio-psychological perceptions with blood plasma constantly hitting on the grey and white matter through the neuron network. Even though there seems to be no compatible correlations between the scales of celestial motions and humanity, the natural forces' exertion to earth may have a correlation to the nuclear forces of human biochemistry, hence the element of subjective epistemology [3], between the cosmic fluxes and engravings on individual scientists' consciousness.

By the three factors categorized in Tables 1 and 2 summarizes the experiment design proposed in the hypothesis, conceptualizing the human factor as biochemical entropy on an individual basis of brain development in time-passing, with the environmental factor confined to inside of earth's atmosphere as horizontal plots. The non-human factor is thence the confounding variable in the protocol designs for sample selection in the experiment. The environmental factor as baseline in adjacent residents hence becomes the null hypothesis for [un] consciousness, and professionals in sports and martial arts the alternative hypothesis. The alternative hypothesis replaced the RNA correlations in the immunohistochemistry method [4], changing the individual presumptions in their studies to an adjacent environmental presumption, and put gravitational effects on earth's thermal pressures into the considerations of grey matter cleavages' and neurites' formation [10-12].

From the experiment design in Table 2, the vertical axis of individual data extracted from environmental factor can further be studied on neurite-soma balance in neuritogenesis with the natural axonal guidance signalling in the participants with different conscious experiences, which may be a factor contributed

to Pertz, et al. [13], studies that "the neurite enrichment of Rac/Cdc42 effectors does not necessarily correlate with the spatially increased GTPase activity" for further pathway analysis, especially with observational cosmologists' relatively concentrated direct interactions with cosmic rays through mostly electromagnetic apparatus in receptive consciousness and scientists working in particle accelerator experiments. The biochemical experiment can be an epistemological study on the consciousness structural gaps between scientific activities and public outreach, and between laboratory physics and astronomical and cosmological sciences with the physio-chemistry differences in psychological time perception and objective mapping on the consciousness structure of time in SI unit indicators. Even though by scientific limitations, we know special relativity only partially explains the universe, the effects being in time with human consciousness may give a more clue of evidence on how much the subjective consciousness may contribute to bias with a psychological experiment design furthering the accuracy of the works in [4]. The cosmological time series will relate the proton decay momenta in global distribution to the hydro and ferrum fluid biochemistry for vertical analysis on individual differences in receptive consciousness differences in Table 1 [5]. Differences in gender and sexuality in the consciousness structures in developmental psychology will be taken accounted for in the interference pattern effects as the neuron web excitation differences to soma and cell membrane [14,15]. Mini hydrolysis observations will mainly depend on PET in the experiment, if no further options are available with existing technologies.

Data collection instruments

The main data collection instruments are MRI, EGG, and PET. Overcoming microscopic van der Waals force in biochemical data collection is the primary reason for the adoption of the mixed method in instrument. MRI techniques are mainly used for hydrophathy intensities in developmental biochemistry. EGGs are used for the detections of continuous and discontinuous elements of brainwaves, with relation to neurological functions [16]. PET is used for florescent paths in proton decay through overlapping nodes with MRI techniques [17]. The electrolyte data combined with PET can map atomic and subatomic structural dynamics in the anatomic functions of human physiology with relation to conscious phenomena.

RESULTS

Data collection plan

Ideally the dependent variables are to be sampled by archives of hospital data so that the time series are variable with a larger spatial base. This will also optimize the costs for experimental trials. The legal procedures necessary for data access with relevant institutions and governmental bodies may replace the direct costs in experimental trial follow-up studies. Another solution is through survey sampling and informed consent on access to individual medical exams. This may reduce bias factors for research integrity.

Analysis plan

An alternative group of lab rats will be introduced in the analysis. The choice of lab rats is considered optimal for: a) Contrast of tailed animals' distribution on earth and similarity to human biology in modern biology and the ice age changes; b) Easier observation for hypothalamic nuclei carbon dimorphism with differences in coccyx varieties; c) The coccyx varieties can be further analysed to determine the sexual dimorphism which is anticipated to be the key ethical debate sociologically on the research results; d) More controllable to correct the factors in cosmological scales and implementation biases in experiment trials; e) Correlate sexual dimorphism and carbon with tail growth. Lenschow, et al. [18], experimentally detected that "cortical genital maps are sexually monomorphic despite genital dimorphism" and "responses of genital neurons were sexually dimorphic" in rat somatosensory cortex. With the hypothesis of parallel structures between human nuclear biochemistry to cosmological orders of change by intensities [4,5], the analysis presumes cosmic proton decay has an active role in neurology and neurological paths in mammals with the derivative in sexual dimorphism of tails. Università di Bologna [19], revelation in the details on the human cerebellum neuronal network "on a scale from 1 micrometre to 0.1 millimetres" "from 5 million to 500 million light-years" on fiber growth poses the difficulties in analysis on how to manage the chronological time scales in possibly different spatial structures, in spite of the nuclear forces' path such as proton decay's probable roles in neurology and neurological paths [4,5].

Table 1: Determination of epistemology in brain biochemistry to the astronomical and cosmological sciences.

Human Factor	Environmental Factor ^a	Non-human Factor ^b
Subjective ontology in unidirectional time	Phenomena of consciousness exposed in social and natural environments	Biochemical stimuli exposure through sensory organs
Neurological development across lifespan	Individual variants in locations	Duration of exposure and receptive consciousness from scientific activities
Sociology of knowledge	Social factors sustaining certain beliefs	Interference of brainwaves to natural waves and instrumentation generated waves

Note: ^a The environment the human subject is in; ^b The subjective interactions of the human subject.

Table 2: Experiment design: Elements of biochemistry in cosmological science.

Comparison Groups	Scientists	Adjacent residents	Professionals in sports and martial arts	Horizontal comparison plots with astrophysics and cosmological data
Autonomic Nervous System/Sympathetic Nervous System	Higher ratio due to denominator ^a	Narrower dispersion in Sympathetic Nervous System ^a	Higher ratio due to numerator ^a	Geometric mean value and determination for non-human factor variations in scientist group
dMRI on white matter dispersion [7] ^b	Determinant for autonomic nervous system between aging and professional activity	Baseline reference for environmental factor	Comparison group for aging and professional differences	Parameterize between baseline and quantitative spatial brains to qualitative study group's variances
fMRI on grey matter structure [10] ^b	Memory recollection on scientific activities during fMRI	Daily activity recollection during fMRI	Motor nerve recollection during fMRI	Comparison between arcsec exposure to observations or data analysis and motor nerve development differences
EKG and PET for particle and nuclear physics brain ^b	Thinking on nuclear and particle analysis and processes during EKG and PET	Thinking on spatial-arrangement relevant activities during EKG and PET	Thinking on force use in sports and martial arts	Finding determinant and intensity between nuclear force in CMB to active and natural differences in brain nuclear activities in consciousness

Note: ^a Expected value; ^b Requires consent for radiological and electromagnetic exposure [11,12].

The solution on the biochemical analysis with radiological tools such as PET would need to utilize the sexual dimorphism's monomorphic responses in the nuclear paths of hormones in the circulatory system [20], in developmental physiology in the resonance chamber(s) of the human body between the hypothalamic nuclei and coccyx (coccygeal vertebra and lateral sacrococcygeal ligament) [21]. This means that a combination between the membranes in nuclear paths with differences between the independent and dependent variables, and their quantitative effects in developmental psychological correlations are needed to minimize the privacy exposure of the participants in data collection, with regard to the effects of cosmoconsciousness and the participants' life trajectories as biochemical carriers vis-à-vis the spatial exposures in cosmological time series. Between the cosmological time series and neurological nuclear traces, String theorists' participation may be of particular interest between [mem] brane and consciousness. With this inference, the analysis will need to treat the nuclear paths in neurology and circulatory targeting as depth perception to the cosmic phenomena, in order to determine the effects of cosmic data to sensory inputs on the subjectivities of scientists' biochemical reactions to consciousness. This may possibly at least differentiate the factors of psychological time from objective phenomena of time free from possible and inevitable biochemical biases in scientific activities. This means that biochemistry and cosmology can be co-corrective, as the preliminary aim in the analysis planned. If sampling locations can be diversified, earth-distributed spatial groups' differentiated local gravity's differences to the cosmological influences may be able to be further analysed physiologically on a quantitative comparative analysis with the resident group as independent variable and other groups as dependent variables. Furthermore, by analysis attempts

in the nuclear targeting physiology in negative time with the SI definition [6], such as from brainwaves, the phenomenology of time in consciousness and in matter definitions may shed new insight on if new indicators can be derived on what time should be in objective epistemology on a cosmic scale. With the continuous and discontinuous cosmic waves from oscillations, the biochemical physiology and targeting paths can be treated as nuclear extraction vessels between attractive and compulsive forces enlarged by developmental psychology, such as phase transitions between conscious and unconscious phenomena.

Stopping criteria

Lab rats trial will be stopped when the initial techniques are proven effective in generating desired results with non-privacy-intrusive safety standards. The lab rats results will be compared with cosmological data to further determine and model key data points in formal experimental trials. In the experiment trials, data collection on individual basis will be stopped by the participant's request, or the key data point gatherings have been met with some room left for further adjustments due to the differences of evolutionary paths. A 1:3:3 ratio on independent and dependent variables is initially planned, with an upper limit of approx. 143 independent variables. The cosmological multi-wavelength data gathering will be optimally collected by observations made in the past 10 years and/or following the independent variables' current activities, given the channels are appropriate with regard to their institutional affiliations and confidentiality in governmental contracts and/or propriety rights. Archival search for astronomical and cosmological data will be conducted according to necessity, especially considering the scientists' focus in different wavelengths.

DISCUSSION

Data analysis process

The MRI, EGG, and PET techniques will generate an electromagnetic or electrolyte map of the internal biochemistry. Parton distribution functions will be run for the data analysis from the electrolyte map, which in anticipation will create a negative map on partons' role in consciousness phenomena. The negative map will be compared within and across the independent and dependent variables. For the independent variables, the negative maps' compatibility with respective spectrum covered by observational cosmologists will be cross-examined, along with those of cosmologists and nuclear scientists. The independent variables' developmental psychology in consciousness shaping of the brain structures will be cross-examined with the dependent variables, and the cosmological and astronomical data will be used as an environmental function to the dependent variables for biochemical influence baselines in global spatial distribution. The motor function's role to consciousness in the dependent variable will be used to compare the developmental psychology of the independent variables from the biochemical influence baselines in global spatial distribution.

Credibility strategies

Political praxis will be introduced for the gender and sexuality facets in consciousness phenomena. Regular peer debriefing will gather feedback in the experiment trial processes, which will enhance the studies. Consensus building and interrater reliability will be conducted with the team and the independent variables in the initial contact and interviews for participation. The debriefing of the research results will also be a feedback to the independent variables' scientific activities uncovering some unconscious contents in the relevant science. The data scientist(s) will play an "auditor" role between the medical and cosmological data, with an assistant for feedback auditing. Triangulation with the similar studies of Vazza, et al. [4], will be conducted especially in the initial and middle phases of the study. Since the study focuses on neuron development from biochemical processes, the path targeting will be more important than optical stimuli from Vazza, et al. [4].

CONCLUSION

I believe that a cosmological theory should be able to explain, at least quantitatively, biology; and by Karl Popper's falsification principle, replacing inter-rater reliability with the positivism in subjective epistemology, the study seeks to reduce the subjective biases in the ranges of cosmological theories with myself included. The direction to the current study may have been influenced by the author's previous report on the thermonuclear contamination of outer space with local black holes and white holes, unconsciously or subconsciously for a salvageable path.

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